

The Impact of Social Customer Relationship Management Capabilities on Firm Performance: The Moderating Role of Social Media Usage in the Manufacturing Sector

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ABSTRACT

As with digital change, social customer relationship management (social CRM) has emerged as the essential strategy to enhance firm performance by combining traditional customer relationship practices with social media technology. The aim of this study is to examine the impact of social CRM capabilities on firm performance with focus on the moderating role of social media usage among medium and large-scale manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District, Sri Lanka. Employing the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Dynamic Capability Theory, capability of social CRM was evaluated by means of information generation and dissemination, and firm performance was evaluated in terms of financial and perceived measures. A standardized questionnaire was utilized to gather data from 160 firms', in which 97 valid responses were obtained. Using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and moderation analysis, the results revealed a strong positive relationship between social CRM capabilities and business performance. The use of social media also moderated the relationship significantly, enhancing the positive effect of social CRM. The results are informative for managers who wish to optimize digital customer engagement strategies and contribute to the current literature on CRM in the context of emerging economies.

Keywords: *Social CRM Capabilities, Social Media Usage, Firm Performance*

1. Background of the Study

In today's competitive environment, businesses increasingly recognize the value of integrating customer relationship management (CRM) with social media to boost engagement and performance. Traditional CRM systems primarily focus on collecting and analyzing customer data to streamline interactions and improve services. However, the rapid expansion of social media platforms has transformed the way businesses and customers interact, leading to the emergence of social CRM. Social customer relationship management (social CRM) extends

traditional CRM by incorporating social media tools, allowing firms to interact with customers in real time, gather feedback, and respond more effectively, driving success (Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri, 2013). Simply, it is used to engage customers in collaborative conversations and enhance customer relationships. For manufacturing companies, social CRM holds particular significance, as these firms often deal with a diverse customer base, including intermediaries, end-users, and service partners. Effective social CRM can help manufacturing firms build trust, manage supply chain relationships, and improve product offerings, ultimately contributing to improved firm performance as the users rely on social media platforms to exchange brand and product related information (Jeswani, 2023).

Social media platforms, like Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram, have become essential tools for implementing social CRM strategies due to their vast reach, interactivity, and data-driven capabilities. Social media technologies create environments that can engage customers in collaborative conversations and enhance customer relationships. Firms that are highly active on social media can raise awareness and underscore their intentions to involve customers in an interactive dialogue that should evaluate the influence of their social CRM capabilities (Kim & Wang, 2018). Organizations with high levels of social media usage are more likely to adapt to the social media environment and achieve an advantage by acquiring customer information and trust before their competitors. Besides, for enhancing social CRM capabilities, organizations need to have the right level of social media activities to achieve organizational performance (Alshourah, Jodeh, Swiety, & Ismail, 2022).

While extensive research has established a clear link between CRM practices and firm performance, the role of social CRM capabilities in driving organizational success is still an emerging area of interest. Anyway, some researchers emphasize that there is a potential moderating effect of social media usage on the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance (Kim & Wang, 2018). Alawan, Rana, Dwivedi, & Algharabat, (2017) reported that about 91% of researchers supported social media as a new instrument that could help an organization maintain its relationship with target customers and enhance organizational performance.

The manufacturing sector in developing countries like Sri Lanka is rapidly adopting digital technologies. Firms in Sri Lanka are increasingly using social CRM to enhance customer relations and efficiency (Gurunathasivam, Samarasinghe, & Kuruppu, 2023). Understanding the moderating role of social media usage in enhancing social CRM capabilities could provide valuable insights for manufacturing companies in the Kurunegala District. It may highlight best practices for integrating social media into CRM strategy and provide guidelines on how to maximize its impact on firm performance. This study aims to investigate how social media usage moderates the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance, with a particular focus on medium and large-scale manufacturing companies in the Kurunegala District.

2. Research Questions

1. What is the level of social CRM capabilities, firm performance, and social media usage in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District?
2. What is the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District?
3. What is the impact of social CRM capabilities on firm performance in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District?
4. What is the moderating effect of social media usage on the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District?

3. Research Objectives

1. To identify the level of social CRM capabilities, firm performance, and social media usage in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District.
2. To examine the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District.
3. To investigate the impact of social CRM capabilities on firm performance in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District.
4. To assess the moderating effect of social media usage on the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District.

4.LITERATURE REVIEW

4.1 Social Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Capabilities

As a new approach in the modern business scenario, CRM has been implemented as social customer relationship management that helps to create customers' interest in products and services offered by the companies through social media platforms (Arora, Singh, Bhatt, & Sharma, 2021). It is one of the most up-to-date business trends and it introduces new channels of two-way communication with customers through social media sites such as Facebook, Twitter, etc. Social CRM provides a method for companies to interact with customers in an easy and modern way directly, while tracking customers' interactions and their influence on social media (Paliouras & Siakas, 2017). Trainor (2012, p. 321) defines social CRM as *"the integration of traditional customer-facing activities with emergent social media applications to engage customers in collaborative conversations and enhance customer relationships."* Similarly, Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013) defined social CRM as the "integration of customer-facing activities, including processes, systems, and technologies, with emergent social media applications in an effort to engage customers in collaborative conversations to enrich customer relationships".

In the present scenario, social CRM is a most essential strategy for customer engagement and customer interaction due to cutthroat competition, and technological advancement of the customer needs and preferences (Tiruwa & Yadav, 2015). Adoption of social CRM practices is most effective in building a sustainable customer relationship and improvement of customer experience (Chou, 2014). It also helps to reach new potential customers, retain existing customers, and mutually beneficial relationships with customers (Geetha, 2024). According to Greenberg (2010), the term social CRM has recently emerged to describe a new way of developing and maintaining customer relationships. He said that social CRM capabilities are unique combinations of emergent technological resources and customer-centric management systems that extend the traditional CRM capabilities by integrating social functions and processes emerging from firm–customer interactions as well as customer–customer interactions.

Kim & Wang (2018) define Social CRM capability as the efficiency of a firm in integrating and converting social media marketing resources into desired sales revenue and customer-relationship outcomes. This definition has brought out the functional dimension of social CRM capability, relating to the transformation of resources into measurable results. Building on this, Trainor (2012) extends the conceptualization of social CRM capability by emphasizing its integrative role in bringing together traditional customer-facing processes, systems, and technologies with emergent social media applications.

4.1.1 Information Generation

Kim & Wang (2018) have focused on how social media is an advanced resource environment in the capture of customer-related information. Such generation of information gets empowered by advanced analytics, machine learning, and artificial intelligence, which can enable the processing of unstructured data- customer comments and feedback, for example, over various social media platforms to information that firms can act upon (Chatterjee, Rana, Tamilmani, & Sharma, 2021). The studies by Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013) also establish that success in information generation depends on the technological preparedness of the firm and the integration of social media tools with existing CRM systems. According to Kim & Wang (2018), the firms that can generate more information from social media can take proactive actions regarding identifying customer needs and market trends, thus offering personalized services while retaining a competitive advantage.

4.1.2 Information Dissemination

Effective dissemination of information means that insights developed from social media and CRM systems are distributed across relevant organizational units for decision-making. According to Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013), the effective integration of social media into traditional CRM technologies remains critical in ensuring that actionable insights reach the right stakeholders on time. Lee, Tao, Li, & Sun (2020) further indicate that internal communication practices and culture are significant ways through which information sharing and utilization are effectively realized within a firm. In the context of social CRM, information dissemination extends beyond internal sharing. Companies also use social media platforms to engage customers directly, sharing tailored information that fosters deeper customer relationships and enhances brand loyalty (Harrigan, Evers, Miles, & Daly, 2018).

4.2 Social Media Usage

Social media have been generally described as those platforms that allow user generated content and in real-time peer-to-peer interaction (Go & You, 2016). More precisely, Go & You (2016) define social media as "a set of internet and mobile tools and applications that stimulate interpersonal communication and opinion sharing, and the production and circulation of user-generated content. Social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, and Pinterest are considered one of the most popular and powerful applications in the digital space. Indeed, these applications have revolutionized the way people communicate with each other, disseminate information, and interact with content (Nanjappan & Deshmukh, 2013; Greenberg, 2010). As Greenberg (2010) also points out, social media has changed modern communication by allowing for interactive, real-time connectivity and content development.

According to Nanjappan & Deshmukh (2013), applications of social media such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube have integrated into the ways of everyday living that the modern individual exists, to the extent that it serves not only for communicating but also for creating and sharing information in a collaborative manner.

Organizations worldwide are increasingly adopting social media technologies for a range of business purposes, including worker collaboration, business intelligence, and customer relationship management (Ainin, Parveen, Moghavvemi, & Jaafar, 2015). Of these, social media technologies have become one of the hottest tools that enable businesses, whether small or large, to hold two-way communications with their customers in cost-effective marketing, promotion, and sales (Ainin, Parveen, Moghavvemi, & Jaafar, 2015). Nowadays, social media technologies have innovatively changed the traditional way of CRM strategy and have facilitated a new kind of interaction between customers and businesses (Malthouse, Haenlein, Skiera, Wege, & Zhang, 2013). According to Kim & Wang (2018) firms using social media actively can also raise awareness and stress the desire to engage customers in dialogue, which should enhance the power of their social CRM capabilities. Social media channels are an excellent platform that can be utilized in order to communicate with customers and gain valuable information from them (Appel, Grewal, Hadi, & Stephen, 2019). Furthermore, organizations that are highly using social media adapt themselves to the social media environment and gain an advantage in acquiring customer information and trust before their competitors (Kim & Wang, 2018).

The major types of social media tools that can be utilized by firms in order to manage their interactions with every category of stakeholder include blogs, social networking sites, collaborative projects, content communities, virtual social worlds, and virtual game worlds (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). More specifically, the use of SMT enables interaction, allows collaboration between business partners and customers, and also creates new business models and new ways of value creation (Nath, Nachiappan, & Ramanathan, 2010). According to (Vlachakis, Siakas, & Naaranoja, 2015), more and more businesses tend to use social media for the purpose of advertising their brand and their products and for better communication with consumers. Similarly, the fundamental nature of social media as a platform for consumers to interact with and influence one another has a more direct impact on brand communities, and it produces higher response rates and greater customer engagement than traditional marketing methodologies that focus only on firm consumer relationship (Riley, 2020).

4.3 Firm Performance

Firm performance is a multidimensional concept commonly evaluated using both financial and non-financial metrics. Financial measures include profitability, return on investment, and market share, while non-financial indicators encompass customer satisfaction, operational efficiency, and customer retention (Mashovic, 2018). This dual approach provides a holistic view of a firm's success in achieving its strategic objectives. From the perspective of social CRM, the performance of a firm is related to the level of ability of an organization to utilize customer data from social networks. Social CRM capabilities let the organization gather, analyze, and apply customer insights that could substantially provide insight into business strategies and improve operational efficiency (Kim & Wang, 2018). As claimed by Kim & Wang (2018), such integration of customer intelligence into strategic decision-making results in an improvement in both financial and non-financial performances. Harris (2001) defined firm performance as the degree at which an organization attains its market-oriented and financial objectives. Social CRM capabilities enable firms to be more responsive to customer needs in a timely and personalized manner. This responsiveness will lead to an increase in customer satisfaction and retention, thus driving brand loyalty, which will translate into better financial outcomes (Malthouse, Haenlein, Skiera, Wege, & Zhang, 2013).

There is, however, empirical evidence supporting such a link between social CRM and firm performance. For example, (Harrigan, Evers, Miles, & Daly, 2018) establish that firms using social CRM exhibit enhanced customer relationship quality and loyalty, both factors having a positive impact on financial performance. Furthermore, Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013) prove that the integration of social media tools into CRM systems enables an increase in the degree of a firm's customer engagement, which improves customer satisfaction and increases the return on investment. Moreover, firms that effectively use social CRM to manage customer interactions tend to outperform competitors by fostering deeper customer engagement and building a robust competitive advantage (Choudhury & Harrigan, 2014). These firms achieve better operational efficiency by streamlining customer interaction processes and aligning them with their broader organizational goals.

4.3.1 Financial Performance

Financial performance encompasses various quantifiable economic outputs, such as profitability, revenue growth, return on investment, and market share (Mashovic, 2018). It represents a key indicator of a firm's competitive position and overall sustainability. As observed by Malthouse, Haenlein, Skiera, Wege, & Zhang (2013), social CRM capabilities enable firms to acquire customer insights necessary for the optimization of marketing strategies and enhanced revenue generation. Those organizations that can

integrate social CRM into social media platforms tend to be more profitable and ensure a better return on investment. For instance, Harrigan, Evers, Miles, & Daly (2018) established that firms using social CRM tools have better customer retention and loyalty, which in turn means revenue growth. Besides, according to Kim & Wang (2018), the personal and timely response via social CRM results in higher customer satisfaction, which then can be transformed into better financial performance. Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013) note that strategic alignment of social media with organizational objectives positively influences financial performance through the reduction of operational costs and enhanced efficiency of marketing activities.

4.3.2 Perceived Performance

Perceived performance refers to subjective evaluations of an organization's success based on stakeholders' perceptions, including employees, customers, and partners. It encompasses dimensions such as service quality, customer satisfaction, brand reputation, and innovation capability (Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1986). In the context of social CRM, perceived performance refers to an organization's ability to meet customer expectations and adapt to market demands. According to Choudhury & Harrigan (2014), firms using social CRM in developing better relationships with customers are perceived as more customer-oriented and innovative, adding value to the firm's reputation and strengthening its position in the market. Furthermore, Kim & Wang (2018) demonstrate that an organization capable of using social media to effectively engage customers and obtain valuable insights is perceived as more responsive and reliable and thus can command trust and loyalty.

4.4. Social CRM Capabilities and Firm Performance

Kim & Wang (2018) stated that social CRM capabilities significantly enhance firm performance with a greater inclination toward financial outcomes. This is further supported by other studies indicating that SCRM capabilities are strong predictors of firm performance when combined with social media use. Previous studies have established that SCRM initiatives are linked to enhanced customer and financial performance of a firm. Several recent studies confirm this, such as Al-Shourah & Al-Shourah (2020), Charoensukmongkol & Sasatanun, (2017), Chuang (2020), Wang & Kim (2017) also established that SCRM is an essential tool for maintaining long-term relationships with customers, hence largely influencing growth and profitability. This is particularly relevant in the context of SMEs because, according to Ahani, Rahim, & Nilashi (2017), SCRM enhances customer relationships and supports sustainable performance improvement.

The integration of social media with CRM systems enhances firm-level capabilities, accordingly improving firm performance, argue Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013). This process aligns with the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory, which emphasizes the importance of firm-specific capabilities, such as customer information systems, organizational structures, and supportive incentives, in driving competitive advantage and performance (Olayah, 2019; Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri, 2013). Investments in marketing and information technology, when integrated, create new capabilities that enhance firm performance (Malthouse, Haenlein, Skiera, Wege, & Zhang, 2013; Mithas, Ramasubbu, & Sambamurthy, 2011; Nath, Nachiappan, & Ramanathan, 2010); Rapp, Trainor, & Agnihotri, 2010). Social CRM capabilities, through their ability to process and utilize customer insights effectively, lead to increased customer retention, higher satisfaction, and better financial outcomes (Kim & Wang, 2018). Therefore, based on the above review, the hypothesis developed was,

H₁: There is a positive relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.

4.5. The Moderating Effect of Social Media Usage

Specifically, social media usage has been found to be a very critical moderating factor in the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance. As Wang and Kim (2017) note, social media usage will actually strengthen the positive effect of social CRM capabilities on firm performance by enhancing customer engagement and making marketing strategies more efficient. Similarly, Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013) identified that social media tools create opportunities to engage in firms with customers in real time, gather insights that are actionable, and develop much better customer relationships, hence enhancing organizational performance. Alalwan, Rana, Dwivedi, & Algharabat (2017), underlined that 91% of the research advocates for social media as an effective tool in maintaining customer relationships and driving firm performance. Social media use enables interactivity between customer information processing and activities of social CRM; this will lead to enhanced customer-linking capabilities and organizational performance (Rapp, Trainor, & Agnihotri, 2010).

Alshourah, Jodeh, Swiety, & Ismail (2022) highlight that an appropriate level of social media activity is decisive for organizations to recognize the full potential of the social CRM capability and enhance firm performance. Kim & Wang (2018) also affirm that social media use is crucial in aligning strategic and technological resources, which is very critical for organizational success. Therefore, based on the above arguments, the hypothesis developed was,

H₂: Social media usage moderates the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.

5. Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is described as a set of broad ideas and principles taken from relevant field of enquiry and used to structure a subsequent presentation (Smyth, 2004). Based on the review of theoretical and empirical literature, a conceptual framework is proposed depicting the social media usage moderate the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.

Figure 3.1: Conceptual Framework

(Source: Kim & Wang, 2018)

6. Hypothesis

H₁: There is a positive relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.

H₂: Social media usage moderates the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.

7. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

7.1 Population

The target population for this research will include managers and executives in medium and large-scale manufacturing firms located in the Kurunegala District, particularly those involved in CRM and social media strategy. The total population comprises 160 manufacturing firms,

comprising the executives and managers who are knowledgeable about the CRM system and social media strategies in the respective organizations.

7.2 Sample and Sampling Technique

A probability sampling technique, specifically simple random sampling, is employed and the study aims to collect data from approximately 114 manufacturing firms. Data will be collected from managers and executives who are responsible for CRM practices and social media strategies within their organizations.

7.2.1 Sample Size

The sample size was estimated by using the following equation.

Equation.1: Sample Size

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} = \frac{160}{1 + 160 \times 0.05^2} = 114$$

Based on this calculation, the required sample size was 114 manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District. However, to account for potential non-responses and incomplete questionnaires, a total of 160 questionnaires were issued. The Table 1 shows a summary of it.

Table.1: Sample Framework

Questionnaires Issued	Questionnaires Received	
	Total	%
160	97	60.63%

(Source: Developed by the researcher for study purposes)

7.3 Data Collection Method

The data collection method for this study is the primary data collection through the administration of a structured questionnaire to managers and executives of medium and large-scale manufacturing companies in the Kurunegala District. It helps in acquiring firsthand information from those who actively take part in implementing social customer relationship management (SCRM) practices and social media strategies of organizations.

8. DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

8.1 Analysis of Reliability

Reliability is the reproducibility or consistency of the measurements in research. It is the degree to which an instrument measures in the same way each time it is used under the same conditions. High reliability means that the instrument is measuring in a consistent way over time, across observers, and across sets of items. According to Creswell (2009), reliability refers to the consistency of scores that are obtained when a research instrument is administered repeatedly. The instrument is reliable if there is consistency in the scores.

In quantitative research, Cronbach's alpha is the most commonly used internal consistency reliability measure. An alpha level of 0.70 or more is generally acceptable (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). In exploratory studies, for instance, 0.60 is also acceptable.

Table 2. Shows the reliability of the variables. The Cronbach's Alpha value of information generation was 0.774, information dissemination was 0.728, financial performance was 0.733, perceived performance was 0.783, and social media usage was 0.800. All the variables had an acceptable reliability.

Table 2: Reliability Analysis for Overall Variables

Variable	Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha Values	No. of Items	Decision
SCRM Capabilities	Information Generation	0.774	3	Accept
	Information Dissemination	0.728	4	Accept
Firm Performance	Financial Performance	0.733	5	Accept
	Perceived Performance	0.783	3	Accept
Social Media Usage		0.800	6	Accept

(Source: Developed for study purposes using survey data)

8.2 Analysis of Validity

Validity refers to the extent to which a measurement instrument accurately captures the concept it purports to measure (Leung, 2015). Construct validity, which assesses the degree to which a scale measures the theoretical construct it is designed to measure, is commonly examined through factor analysis. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity

are used to determine the appropriateness of factor analysis. KMO values greater than 0.6 and significant Bartlett's test results ($p < 0.05$) indicate that the data is suitable for factor analysis (Taherdoost, 2016). Table 2 presents the validity statistics for the study variables.

Table 3: Validity

Variable	Dimension	KMO Value	Bartlett's Test	Decision
SCRM Capabilities	Information Generation	0.702	0.000	Accept
	Information Dissemination	0.751	0.000	Accept
Firm Performance	Financial Performance	0.702	0.000	Accept
	Perceived Performance	0.703	0.000	Accept
Social Media Usage		0.805	0.000	Accept

(Source: Survey Data)

The KMO values for all variables are above the 0.6 threshold, ranging from 0.702 for information generation (ING) and financial performance (FP) to 0.805 for social media usage (SMU). The Bartlett's test results are also significant ($p = 0.000$) for all variables. These findings suggest that the sample size is adequate, and the data have sufficient correlations to proceed with factor analysis. The validity analysis confirms that the measurement scales used in this study possess construct validity and are appropriate for measuring the intended variables.

8.3 Data Presentation

Questionnaires were issued to 160 respondents in the manufacturing sector in Kurunegala District. However, 97 responses were received from them. It was considered as the sample and it includes two parts, namely personal information & research information. The data was presented by using frequency distributions.

8.3.1 Data Presentation for Personal Information

The demographic information was analyzed using descriptive analysis. The questions on personal information concern the following respondent's significant personal information.

8.3.1.1 Age

Out of 97 respondents of the sample, 15.5% of respondents were between the age of 18 – 24 years, 39.2% of respondents were between the age of 25 – 34 years, 27.8% of respondents were between the age of 35 – 44 years, 13.4% of respondents were between the age of 45 – 54 years, and 4.1% of respondents were the age of 55 and above. Most of respondents were between the age of 25 – 34 years.

8.3.1.2 Gender

Out of 97 respondents of the sample, 49.5% of respondents were male, and 50.5% respondents were female.

8.3.1.3 Educational Level

Out of 97 respondents of the sample, 1% of respondent had studied up to G.C.E. O/L, 9.3% of respondents had studied up to G.C.E. A/L, 20.6% of respondents had studied up to Diploma level, 53.6% of respondents had studied up to Bachelor's Degree level, and 15.5% of respondents had studied up to Master's Degree or Higher. Most of the respondents had studied up to the Bachelor's Degree level.

8.3.1.4 Job Title

Out of 97 respondents of the sample, 13.4% of respondents were Managing Directors, 7.2% of respondents were Directors, 14.4% of respondents were Department Managers, 14.4% of respondents were Assistant Managers, 15.5% of respondents were Team Leaders, 9.3% of respondents were Senior Executives, and other 25.8% of respondents were Junior Executives.

8.3.1.5 Years the Business has been Operational

Out of 97 respondents of the sample, 33% of manufacturing firms had been operational between 1 – 5 years, 41.2% of manufacturing firms had been operational between 6 – 10 years, and other 25.8% of manufacturing firms had been operational more than 10 years.

8.3.1.6 Number of Employees

Out of 97 respondents of the sample, 78.4% of manufacturing firms were medium scale firms, and other 21.6% of manufacturing firms were large scale firms.

8.3.1.7 Type of Manufacturing

Out of 97 respondents of the sample, 17.5% of manufacturing firms were categorized under textile & apparel sector, 16.5% of manufacturing firms were categorized under food & beverage sector, 12.4% of manufacturing firms were categorized under construction material & ceramics sector, 9.3% of manufacturing firms were categorized under rubber & plastic products sector, 13.4% of manufacturing firms were categorized under wood & furniture sector, and 30.9% of manufacturing firms were under other sectors.

8.4. Data Presentation for Research Information

Research information considers the main variables that SCRM capabilities, FPF, and SMU. There were seven items used for measure SCRM capabilities under the independent variable, whereas six items in SMU measure the moderate variable. And also, the dependent variable too has been measured by eight items to evaluate FPF among the manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District. The Univariate and Bivariate analyses were conducted to analyze the research objectives.

8.4.1 Univariate Analysis

In this study, mean was used to measure the central tendency while dispersion is described by using standard deviation. Measures of central tendency encapsulate in one figure a value that is typical for a distribution of values (Bryman & Bell, 2016). Under univariate analysis, researcher analyses the degree of variables, dimensions and indicators by using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation in order to find out the results regarding objective one.

The first objective is “To identify the level of social CRM capabilities, firm performance, and social media usage in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District.”

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Variables

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Social CRM Capabilities	4.1546	0.5423
Firm Performance	4.3544	0.4299
Social Media Usage	4.1581	0.5386

(Source: Survey Data)

8.4.1.1. Level of Social CRM Capabilities

Table 4 shows that the mean value of Social CRM Capabilities is 4.1546, and it deviates from 0.5423. As the mean value is between 3.5 and 5, the level of social CRM Capabilities was at a high level.

Table 5: Decision Criteria and Frequency Distribution of SCRM Capabilities

	Decision Attributes	Frequency	Percent
1.0≤X≤2.5	Low Level	4	4.1%
2.5<X≤3.5	Moderate Level	5	5.2%
3.5<X≤5.0	High Level	88	90.7%
Total		97	100%
Mean = 4.1546		Std: Deviation = 0.5423	

(Source: Survey Data)

There is a high level of social CRM capabilities according to the respondents of manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District (Mean = 4.1546). In addition, most of the respondents expressed a common opinion regarding the variable of social CRM capabilities (SD = 0.5423). It is also noted that about 90.7% of respondents had a high level, 5.2% of respondents had a moderate level, and 4.1% of respondents had a low level.

Here, two dimensions: information generation (ING) and information dissemination (IND) have the mean values of 4.3093 and 4.0387, with the standard deviation of 0.6259 and 0.5922, respectively. Table 5.13 shows that it has a high level of ING, IND, and overall SCRM Capabilities.

Table 6: Level of SCRM Capabilities’ Dimensions – ING & IND

Variable / Dimension	Decision Criteria	Mean	SD	Level
Information Generation	3.5<X≤5.0	4.3093	0.6259	High
Information Dissemination	3.5<X≤5.0	4.0387	0.5922	High
Social CRM Capabilities	3.5<X≤5.0	4.1546	0.5423	High

(Source: Survey Data)

8.4.1.2 Level of Firm Performance

Table 4 shows that the mean value of Firm Performance is 4.3544, and it deviates from 0.4299. As the mean value is between 3.5 and 5, the level of Firm Performance was at a high level.

Table 7: Decision Criteria and Frequency Distribution of FPF

	Decision Attributes	Frequency	Percent
$1 \leq X \leq 2.5$	Low Level	0	0%
$2.5 < X \leq 3.5$	Moderate Level	4	4.1%
$3.5 < X \leq 5$	High Level	93	95.9%
Total		97	100%
Mean = 4.3544		Std: Deviation = 0.4299	

(Source: Survey Data)

There is a high level of Firm Performance according to the respondents of manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District (Mean = 4.3544). In addition, most of the respondents expressed a common opinion regarding the variable of firm performance (SD = 0.4299). It is also noted that about 95.9% of respondents had a high level, and 4.1% of respondents had a moderate level.

Here, two dimensions: financial performance (FP) and perceived performance (PP) have the mean values of 4.3381 and 4.3814, with the standard deviation of 0.4419 and 0.5336, respectively. Table 5.15 shows that it has a high level of ING, IND, and overall SCRM Capabilities.

Table 8: Level of Firm Performance Dimensions – FP & PP

Variable / Dimension	Decision Criteria	Mean	SD	Level
Financial Performance	$3.5 < X \leq 5.0$	4.3381	0.4419	High
Perceived Performance	$3.5 < X \leq 5.0$	4.3814	0.5336	High
Firm Performance	$3.5 < X \leq 5.0$	4.3544	0.4299	High

(Source: Survey Data)

8.4.1.3 Level of Social Media Usage

Table 4 shows that the mean value of social media usage is 4.1581, and it deviates from 0.5386. As the mean value is between 3.5 and 5, the level of social media usage was at a high level.

Table 9: Decision Criteria and Frequency Distribution of SMU

	Decision Attributes	Frequency	Percent
$1 \leq X \leq 2.5$	Low Level	3	3.1%
$2.5 < X \leq 3.5$	Moderate Level	5	5.2%
$3.5 < X \leq 5$	High Level	89	91.8%
Total		97	100%
Mean = 4.1581		Std: Deviation = 0.5386	

(Source: Survey Data)

There is a high level of social media usage according to the respondents of manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District (Mean = 4.1581). In addition, most of the respondents expressed a common opinion regarding the variable of social media usage (SD = 0.5386). It is also noted that about 91.8% of respondents had a high level, 5.2% of respondents had a moderate level, and 3.1% of respondents had a low level.

Table 10: Level of SCRM Capabilities, FPF, and SMU Sector Wise

Type of Manufacturing		SCRM Capabilities	FPF	SMU
Textile & Apparel	Mean	4.2941	4.4338	4.2941
	Std. Deviation	0.39276	0.4422	0.37048
Food & Beverage	Mean	3.9821	4.2031	4.125
	Std. Deviation	0.63003	0.58962	0.57252
Construction Material & Ceramics	Mean	4.2619	4.3750	4.1806
	Std. Deviation	0.30356	0.3198	0.19408
Rubber & Plastic Products	Mean	4.3333	4.3889	4.4815
	Std. Deviation	0.28571	0.35047	0.21155
Wood & Furniture	Mean	4.0549	4.2981	4.0128
	Std. Deviation	0.64823	0.32491	0.6613
Other	Mean	4.1143	4.3958	4.0556
	Std. Deviation	0.6349	0.43312	0.66571
Total	Mean	4.1546	4.3544	4.1581
	Std. Deviation	0.54229	0.42987	0.53865

(Source: Survey Data)

Category-wise comparison shows that social CRM capabilities, firm performance, and social media usage are high across all manufacturing sectors. For social CRM capabilities, the Rubber & Plastic Products sector returned the highest value (M = 4.33), while the lowest was for the Food & Beverage sector (M = 3.98). For firm performance, the Textile & Apparel sector ranked the highest (M = 4.43), whereas the lowest was in the Food & Beverage sector (M = 4.20). For social media usage, the Rubber & Plastic Products sector ranked the highest in terms of its mean (M = 4.48), whereas the lowest was in the Wood & Furniture sector (M = 4.01).

8.4.2. Bivariate Analysis

The bivariate analysis has been used to analysis of data measured on two variables. The bivariate analysis includes the regression analysis and correlation analysis. Bivariate correlation has been used to tests the relationship among variables. In this study, the researcher conducted the Correlation analysis under bivariate analysis in order to find out the results regarding objective two.

Second objective is “To examine the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District.”

8.4.2.1 Pearson’s Correlation Analysis

The Pearson’s correlation analysis is used to identify the relationship between two or more variables. And also, the Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) was computed to test the direction and strength of the relationship exist among the study variables.

Table 11: Correlation among Social CRM Capabilities, and Firm Performance (FPF)

		SCRM Capabilities	FPF	SMU
SCRM Capabilities	Pearson Correlation			
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	97		
FPF	Pearson Correlation	.565**		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	97	97	
SMU	Pearson Correlation	.758**	.607**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	97	97	97

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

(Source: Survey Data)

According to the Table 11, the correlation coefficient (r) value was 0.565 between SCRM Capabilities and FPF at the 0.01 significance levels. Also, between SCRM Capabilities, FPF and SMU has the correlation coefficient (r) 0.758 and 0.607 at the 0.01 significant level respectively. Moreover, the value of the correlation coefficient falls under the coefficient range of 0.5-1.0. The p-value is equal to 0.000 and less than Alpha value. It shows that there is a strong positive relationship between SCRM Capabilities and Firm Performance.

8.4.2.2 Simple Regression Analysis

Simple Linear Regression is a statistical tool used to examine the relationship between one predictor (independent) variable and a single quantitative response (dependent) variable. Simple linear regression analysis produces a regression equation that can be used for prediction. In this study, the researcher conducted a Simple Regression analysis in order to find out the results regarding objective three.

The third objective is “To investigate the impact of social CRM capabilities on firm performance in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District.”

8.4.2.2. 1 Impact of Social CRM Capabilities on Firm Performance

Table 12: Model Summary of Regression Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.565 ^a	0.319	0.312	0.35649	1.576

a Predictors: (Constant), Social CRM Capabilities

b Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

(Source: Survey Data)

According to Table 12, the R² indicates that SCRM capabilities explains approximately 31.9% of the variance in firm performance, with adjusted R² = 31.2%. There was independence of residuals, as assessed by a Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.576.

Table 13: ANOVA of Regression Model

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.667	1	5.667	44.592	.000 ^b
	Residual	12.073	95	0.127		
	Total	17.74	96			

a Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

b Predictors: (Constant), Social CRM Capabilities

(Source: Survey Data)

The results in Table 13 indicate that Social CRM capabilities ($p < 0.05$) significantly impact on firm performance. A statistically significant result also indicates that there is a statistically significant linear relationship. So, social CRM capabilities statistically significantly predict firm performance ($F(1, 95) = 44.592, p < .05$).

Table 14: Coefficients of Regression Model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.493	0.281		8.869	.000
	SCRM Capabilities	0.448	0.067	0.565	6.678	.000

a Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

(Source: Survey Data)

The β coefficient of social CRM capabilities is 0.448. The β coefficient shows that for every unit of increase in SCRM capabilities, there is an increase of 0.448 units in Firm Performance. The p-value (0.000) is compared to the chosen alpha level (0.05). It explains that the β value for SCRM capabilities was statistically significant for making decisions.

8.4.2. 3 Hierarchical Regression Analysis

Hierarchical regression analysis is a statistical technique used to determine the contribution of one or more independent variables in the prediction of a dependent variable, added to the regression equation in steps or blocks. Hair, Howard, & Nitzl (2020) explain that hierarchical regression is very useful for

ascertaining moderation effects. In this study, the researcher conducted a simple regression analysis in order to find out the results regarding objective three.

The fourth objective is “To assess the moderating effect of social media usage on the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance in the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District.”

Table 15: Model Summary of Regression Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Change Statistics		
				R Square Change	F Change	Sig. F Change
1	.628 ^a	0.394	0.381	0.394	30.568	.000
2	.688 ^b	0.474	0.457	0.08	14.055	.000

a Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Usage, Social CRM Capabilities

b Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Usage, Social CRM Capabilities, Interaction_SCRMSMU

c Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

(Source: Survey Data)

In Model 1 with social CRM capabilities and social media usage as the predictors, R was 0.628 and R Square was 0.394, indicating that the two variables explained approximately 39.4% of the variation in firm performance. The adjusted R Square was 0.381, and F-change value was significant ($F = 30.568, p < 0.001$), indicating a good fit of the model. For Model 2, the interaction term (Social CRM Capabilities \times Social Media Usage) was added in order to test the moderating effect. The R Square increased to 0.474 and the R Square change was 0.080, indicating that the interaction term provided an explanation of 8% more variance in firm performance. The F-change for the model was 14.055, and the change was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), reflecting the presence of a significant moderating effect.

Table 16: ANOVA of Regression Model

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	37.832	2	18.916	30.568	.000 ^b
	Residual	58.168	94	0.619		
	Total	96	96			
2	Regression	45.469	3	15.156	27.894	.000 ^c
	Residual	50.531	93	0.543		
	Total	96	96			

a Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

b Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Usage, Social CRM Capabilities

c Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Usage, Social CRM Capabilities, Interaction_SCRMSMU

(Source: Survey Data)

In Model 1, the F-value is 30.568, and its significance level (p-value) is 0.000. This means that Model 1 is significant at the 0.01 level and suggests that social CRM capabilities and social media usage together significantly predict firm performance. For Model 2, after adding the interaction term (Social CRM Capabilities \times Social Media Usage), the F-value is 27.894 and $p = 0.000$, again suggesting statistically significant improvement in the model. The low p-values ($p < 0.001$) in both models always indicate that both regression models are highly significant, and the used variables explain a high degree of variance in firm performance. These results support the hypothesis that both the main effects and also the moderating effect contribute notably to the model.

Table 17: Coefficients of Regression Model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.000	.080		.000	1.000
	SCRM Capabilities	.248	.123	.248	2.016	.047
	SMU	.419	.123	.419	3.403	.001
2	(Constant)	-.143	.084		-1.706	.091
	SCRM Capabilities	.369	.120	.369	3.084	.003
	SMU	.687	.136	.687	5.064	.000
	Interaction_SCRMSMU	.191	.051	.465	3.749	.000

a Dependent Variable: Firm Performance

(Source: Survey Data)

Both social CRM capabilities ($\beta = 0.248$, $p = 0.047$) and social media usage ($\beta = 0.419$, $p = 0.001$) are statistically significant and positive in Model 1, indicating that all of the predictors, individually, make a significant contribution towards enhancing firm performance. In Model 2, the interaction term (Social CRM Capabilities \times Social Media Usage) is included to establish the moderating effect. All predictors of Model 2 are statistically significant. social CRM capabilities ($\beta = 0.369$, $p = 0.003$) and social media

usage ($\beta = 0.687$, $p < 0.001$) are both significant with higher standardized beta values, suggesting an even more influential impact when the interaction term is considered. Most significantly, perhaps, the interaction term ($\beta = 0.465$, $p < 0.001$) is highly significant, suggesting that social media usage positively moderates the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.

8.5. Testing Hypotheses

8.5.1 Testing Hypothesis 1

H₁: There is a positive relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.

The correlation coefficient value in Table 10 illustrates that it has a positive relationship between SCRM capabilities and firm performance. The null hypothesis can be rejected because the level of significance (0.00) is smaller than the Alpha value (0.05). It is possible to conclude that there is enough evidence to confirm that there is a positive relationship between SCRM capabilities and firm performance in the manufacturing sector of the Kurunegala District.

8.5.2. Testing Hypothesis 2

H₂: Social media usage moderates the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.

According to Table 15, the interaction term led to a significant increase in R Square ($\Delta R^2 = 0.080$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the interaction contributes explanatory power to the model. Moreover, the interaction term was statistically significant ($\beta = 0.465$, $p < 0.001$), which supports the fact that social media usage significantly moderates the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance (Table 17).

9. Discussion of Research Information

9.1 Objective One

The first objective of the research is to identify the level of social CRM capabilities, firm performance, and social media usage. Hence, this is the main part of the research, where the descriptive analysis was used to analyze the data to come to a conclusion.

9.1.1 Level of Social CRM Capabilities

According to the descriptive analysis, there is a high level of social CRM capabilities among manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District, where the mean is 4.1546 and the standard deviation is 0.5423, reflecting high consensus among the respondents. Remarkably, 90.7% of the respondents showed a high level of social CRM capabilities, while 5.2% rated a moderate level and 4.1% rated a low level. Both the information generation (ING) and information dissemination (IND) aspects of social CRM capabilities also recorded high mean values of 4.3093 and 4.0387, respectively, with standard deviations of 0.6259 and 0.5922. These suggest that it has a high level of ING, IND, and overall SCRM Capabilities.

9.1.2 Level of Firm Performance

According to the descriptive statistics, there is a high level of firm performance among the respondents of the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District, with a mean value score of 4.3544 and a standard deviation of 0.4299. Specifically, 95.9% of the respondents claimed to have a high level of firm performance, 4.1% recorded a moderate level, and no respondent indicated a low level of firm performance. Firm performance was measured with the two dimensions of financial performance (FP) and perceived performance (PP). The mean score for FP was 4.3381 with a standard deviation of 0.4419, and PP also had a mean score of 4.3814 with a standard deviation of 0.5336. These findings confirm both aspects, and the overall construct is rated to be at a high level, indicating that firms are performing well on both objective financial performance and perceived performance.

9.1.3 Level of Social Media Usage

According to the descriptive analysis, there is a high level of social media usage among the respondents of the selected manufacturing firms in Kurunegala District, expressed as a mean of 4.1581 using a five-point Likert scale. A standard deviation of 0.5386 shows a fairly even consensus of opinion of respondents, with a high level of agreement among firms regarding the relevance and use of social media. It is also supported by the response distribution, where 91.8% of the respondents indicated they have a high social media usage, 5.2% have a moderate level, while only 3.1% indicated a low level. This shows that the majority of the manufacturing firms in the region are actively using social media platforms in their business.

9.2 Objective Two

From this part, the researcher tries to achieve the second objective of the research, which refers to examining the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Here, the correlation analysis was made to get the results in order to achieve this objective.

9.2.1 Relationship between SCRM Capabilities and Firm Performance

According to the correlation analysis, the correlation coefficient (r) between social CRM capabilities and firm performance was 0.565 and statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($p = 0.000$). The value is between 0.5 and 1.0, indicating a strong positive correlation between both variables. Since the p -value is below the alpha level of 0.05, the relation is statistically significant. So, the results show that social CRM capabilities are positively and significantly correlated with the firm performance.

Firms that created and disseminated customer information efficiently had higher levels of performance. This supports Harrigan, Evers, Miles, & Daly (2018), who found SCRM tools to enhance loyalty and financial performance, and Choudhury & Harrigan (2014), who found that advanced SCRM routines allow firms to outcompete competitors. Similarly, Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013) highlighted social media use to augment CRM and decision-making effectiveness.

9.3. Objective three

From this part, the researcher tries to achieve the third objective of the research, which refers to investigating the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Here, the simple regression analysis was made to get the results in order to achieve this objective.

9.3.1 Impact of SCRM Capabilities on Firm Performance

The regression analysis indicated that social CRM capabilities explained approximately 31.9% of the variation in firm performance, as depicted by the R^2 value of 0.319, with an adjusted R^2 of 0.312, showing a moderately good fit of the model. The assumption of independence of residuals was met, as ascertained by the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.576, which fell within the tolerance. As revealed in Table 5.20, social CRM capabilities had a significant effect on firm performance ($p < 0.05$), indicating that those two variables had a significant linear relationship. Specifically, the regression model was significant, with $F(1, 95) = 44.592$, $p < 0.05$, which confirmed that the model as a whole significantly predicts firm performance.

The beta (β) coefficient of social CRM capabilities was 0.448, indicating that with an increase in social CRM capabilities by one unit, firm performance increases by approximately 0.448 units. The p-value of 0.000, which is lower than the alpha value of 0.05, also shows that the beta coefficient is statistically significant. The findings show that social CRM capabilities have a significant positive impact on enhancing firm performance in the manufacturing industry in the Kurunegala District. These results are consistent with Kim and Wang (2018), who showed that SCRM enhances measurable outcomes, and Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013), who showed that customer engagement with SCRM is followed by profitability. Malthouse, Haenlein, Skiera, Wege, & Zhang (2013) also determined that the integration of CRM and social media leads to efficiency and revenue growth.

9.4 Objective four

From this part, the researcher tries to achieve the fourth objective of the research, which refers to assessing the moderating effect of social media usage on the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. Here, the hierarchical regression analysis was made to get the results in order to achieve this objective.

9.4.1 Moderating Effect on the Relationship between SCRM Capabilities and FPF

In the hierarchical regression analysis, the interaction term (Social CRM Capabilities \times Social Media Usage) was entered in Model 2. The R Square increased from 0.394 to 0.474, indicating that the interaction explained an additional 8% of the variance in firm performance. The F-change statistic of 14.055 was statistically significant at $p < 0.001$, which validated the model fit enhancement. Furthermore, the interaction term was highly significant ($\beta = 0.465$, $p < 0.001$), showing that social media usage is increasing the positive effect of social CRM capabilities on firm performance. That is, when firms use social media to a greater degree, the effect of social CRM capabilities on performance is enhanced. These findings strongly support the fourth objective and establish the need for leveraging social media as a strategic tool to enhance the performance of CRM in the manufacturing sector.

This finding is supported by Wang & Kim (2017), who observed that social media amplifies CRM performance, and Trainor, Andzulis, Rapp, & Agnihotri (2013), who argued that real-time engagement via social media improves performance. Alalwan, Rana, Dwivedi, & Algharabat (2017) also stressed that social media is a key channel to improve customer relationship and outcomes.

9.5 Discussion of Hypotheses Testing

9.5.1 Testing Hypothesis 1

There is a positive relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance. The null hypothesis can be rejected because the level of significance (0.00) is smaller than the Alpha value (0.05). It is possible to conclude that there is enough evidence to confirm that there is a positive relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance in the manufacturing sector of the Kurunegala District.

9.5.2 Testing Hypothesis 2

According to the results, including the interaction term between social CRM capabilities and social media usage led to a significant R^2 increase ($\Delta R^2 = 0.080$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the interaction contributed significant explanatory power beyond the regression model. This confirms that the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance is enhanced after controlling for the intensity of social media usage. Additionally, the interaction term was significant ($\beta = 0.465$, $p < 0.001$), which confirms that social media usage is a good moderator in the relationship. All these results confirm that social media usage moderates the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance in the manufacturing sector of the Kurunegala District.

Table 18: Summary of Hypotheses Testing

No:	Hypotheses	Decision
H ₁	<i>There is a positive relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.</i>	Accepted
H ₂	<i>Social media usage moderates the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance.</i>	Accepted

(Source: Survey Data)

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

10 Conclusions

Mainly, the researcher has used descriptive analysis, correlation analysis, simple regression analysis, and hierarchical regression analysis to achieve the objectives of this research study. This research study has been conducted using 97 manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District.

10.1 First Objective of the Study

The first objective of the research was to identify the level of social CRM capabilities, firm performance, and social media usage in the manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District. Descriptive analysis revealed a high level of social CRM capabilities (Mean = 4.1546, SD = 0.5423), as 90.7% of the respondents reported high levels. Its dimensions, information generation, and information dissemination also reported high levels (4.3093 and 4.0387, respectively). Firm performance was also rated high (Mean = 4.3544, SD = 0.4299), with 95.9% of the respondents registering good performance on both financial and perceived measures. Social media usage also recorded a high mean of 4.1581 (SD = 0.5386) with 91.8% of the respondents recording active usage. These results confirm that all three variables are present at a high level in the companies surveyed.

10.2 Second Objective of the Study

The second objective of the research was to examine the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance. According to the correlation analysis, there is a high positive and significant correlation between social CRM capabilities and firm performance, $r = 0.565$ ($p = 0.000$). This r-value, being between 0.5 and 1.0, supports a strong correlation. These findings indicate that social CRM capabilities are positively and significantly correlated with improvements in the firm performance of companies.

10.3 Third Objective of the Study

The fourth research objective was to examine the moderating role of social media usage on the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance. To address this, a hierarchical regression was conducted, where the interaction term (Social CRM Capabilities \times Social Media Usage) was added to Model 2. The R Square increased from 0.394 to 0.474, indicating that the interaction accounted for an additional 8% of variance in firm performance. The value of the F-change statistic was 14.055 and was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), thereby confirming that the inclusion of the social

media usage interaction term had a considerable improvement on the model. The interaction term itself was highly significant ($\beta = 0.465$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that social media usage supports the positive effect of social CRM capabilities on firm performance. That is, firms that are presently involved with social media observe a stronger linkage between their CRM efforts and performance outcomes.

10.4 Contribution of the Study

This study makes several contributions to practice and theory. Theoretically, this study contributes to the existing literature by empirically examining the impact of social CRM capabilities on firm performance and the moderating role of social media usage in the setting of manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District. By taking on two critical dimensions, Information Generation and Information Dissemination, the study offers a more complete understanding of how social CRM functions in real business settings. The findings contribute to the growing literature on digital customer relationship management and offer evidence of the value of social media integration into CRM strategies. Practically, the study offers valuable insights to decision-makers and managers in the manufacturing sector, demonstrating that efforts at enhancing social CRM capabilities, particularly when complemented with active social media usage, can yield concrete enhancements in both perceived and financial firm performance. In this regard, the research confirms the use of digital technologies and customer-focused strategies in enabling competitiveness and business success.

10.6 Limitations of the Study

This research has several limitations. First, the research concentrated on medium and large-scale manufacturing firms, thus excluding small-scale industries. Therefore, the findings may not be generalizable to all manufacturing firms, particularly small firms that may face other structural, financial, and technological constraints. Second, the research was geographically restricted to manufacturing firms in the Kurunegala District and could restrict the generalizability of the results to other geographical areas or industries. Third, the data were collected using self-reported questionnaires, which are susceptible to response bias or social desirability bias, which might undermine the validity of the responses. Fourth, the study used a cross-sectional design in which data were gathered at a single point in time, limiting the ability to infer causal relationships between the variables. The study also focused on only two dimensions of social CRM capabilities and firm performance, which may not be rich enough to capture the complexity of these constructs. Follow-up studies could address these limitations with a larger, more diverse sample, longitudinal data, and additional variables or external factors that may contribute to the social CRM capabilities-Firm Performance relationship.

10.7 Recommendations and Future Research Directions

The present study was directed towards assessing the impact of social CRM capabilities on firm performance and the moderating role of social media usage in medium and large-scale manufacturing companies in the Kurunegala District, Sri Lanka. Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed.

- **Increasing Social CRM Capabilities**

The study identified that social CRM capabilities positively affect firm performance. Therefore, manufacturing firms have to focus on improving both information generation and information dissemination processes. This can be achieved by adopting CRM systems that capture real-time customer data, organizing employee training programs in customer data analysis, and fostering cross-functional communication so that valuable customer information is shared across departments.

- **Leveraging Social Media Usage**

Social media use was found to have a strong moderating effect on the relationship between social CRM capabilities and firm performance, strengthening the positive effects. Thus, firms should strategically integrate social media into their customer relationship processes. This includes active presence on websites, seeking feedback from customers, online marketing efforts, and monitoring brand sentiment. Training personnel in social media communication efficacy and customer management can further improve the outcomes.

- **Enabling Data-Driven Decision-Making**

Businesses must use customer information derived from social CRM software and social media analytics to make strategic decisions. Data visualization tools and predictive analytics can be embraced to convert customer knowledge into an actionable strategy and ultimately, performance enhancement.

- **Disseminating CRM Culture Across the Business**

An enterprise-wide CRM mindset needs to be developed in which all departments, not just marketing or customer service, are cognizant of and contribute to customer relationship goals. Workshops, company newsletters, and CRM performance metrics can help to solidify the culture.

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